

FT-002

Molecular Design and Structural Elucidation of a DMAP-Functionalized meso-Arylporphyrin Cobalt(III) Complex: Insights from Spectroscopy and Single-Crystal X-ray Diffraction

Taissir FRADI¹*, Habib NASRI¹¹ Faculty of Sciences of Monastir, Laboratory of physico-chemistry of Materials

*Fraditaysir2017@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author

Cobalt metalloporphyrins have garnered considerable interest among porphyrin-based compounds because of their structural and electrical similarity to vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamin)[1]. Because of their similarities, they have special physicochemical qualities that make them very appealing for a variety of applications [2...5].

In this work, we focused on the synthesis, crystal structure determination by single-crystal X-ray diffraction, and spectroscopic characterization of a new cobalt(III) complex. Using the ligand dimethylaminopyrine (DMAP), we synthesized the complex bis-DMAP Cobalt(III){5,10,15,20-tetrakis[(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)porphyrinato]}, with the formula Complex : [Co^{III}(TTMPP)(DMAP)₂]Cl•3CHCl₃ (I).

Compound (I) crystallizes in the monoclinic crystal system with space group (P21/c). The unit cell parameters are as follows: a = 25,758(5), b = 14,687(3), c = 24,330(5), and β = 117,02(2). Other crystallographic parameters include V = 8200(3) Å³, Z = 4, R1 = 0,0643, wR2 = 0,2141 and S = 1,094.

Keywords: Cobalt, complex, DRX, porphyrin, spectroscopic characterization

1. INTRODUCTION

Porphyrins and their metallated derivatives are a significant class of macrocyclic compounds because of their versatile coordination and customizable electronic characteristics, which support applications in molecular electronics, catalysis, and sensing [6]. Because of their accessible redox states and sensitivity to axial ligation, cobalt porphyrins have garnered special interest. These complexes' supramolecular organization and electrical structure can be greatly impacted by the coordination of nitrogen-donor ligands like 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) [7].

The synthesis and characterisation of cobalt porphyrins have been published in a large number of papers, however most of them concentrate on spectroscopic characteristics or crystallographic data, with little effort made to correlate these aspects. Furthermore, despite their significance in regulating material

stability and characteristics, intermolecular interactions controlling crystal packing are frequently not thoroughly examined.

The synthesis and characterisation of the cobalt(III) porphyrin complex [Co^{III}TTMP (DMAP)₂] are reported in this paper. To determine the connections between molecule structure, spectroscopic behavior, and intermolecular interactions, a combination method utilizing ultraviolet–visible (UV–Vis) and infrared (IR) spectroscopy and single-crystal X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used. The goal of this work is to advance knowledge of the links between structure and properties in cobalt porphyrin complexes.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. synthesis

The starting material [CoII(TTMPP)] (20 mg, 0.019 mmol) and an excess of DMAP (90 mg, 1.32 mmol) were stirred overnight at room temperature in 5 mL of chloroform. The color of the solution changed from violet to blue-green. Crystals were obtained by slow diffusion of *n*-hexane into a dichloromethane solution.

2.2. Methodology

Fourier-transformed IR spectra were recorded on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer. UV-visible spectra were recorded with a WinASPECT PLUS (validation for SPECORD PLUS version 4.2). ¹H NMR spectra were obtained at room temperature on a Bruker 300 Ultrashield spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield from internal tetramethylsilane (TMS). Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) spectra were recorded using an amaZon speed ion trap mass spectrometer. The samples were ionized by electrospray ionization (ESI) under the following conditions: capillary temperature of 320 °C, vaporizer temperature of 320 °C, and sheath gas flow rate of 5 mL/min.

2.3. Computational Methods

The data were collected at 150 K on a D8 VENTURE Bruker AXS CCD diffractometer using MoK α radiation of wavelength 0.71073 Å. The reflections were scaled and corrected for absorption effects by using SADABS program (Bruker AXS 2008) [8]. The structure was solved by direct methods by using SIR-2004 [9] and refined by full-matrix least-squares techniques on F² by using the SHELXL-2014 program [10]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. spectroscopic characterization

The absorption properties of the free-base porphyrin H₂TTMPP exhibit a characteristic electronic spectrum typical of a meso-arylporphyrin. Metallation with cobalt(II) induces a hypsochromic shift of the Soret band, accompanied by a reduction in the number of Q bands. Coordination of the axial ligand DMAP to the parent complex [Co^{II}(TTMPP)] results in a bathochromic shift. This red shift is likely attributed to an increase in π -conjugation upon coordination of the DMAP ligand.

The free porphyrin H₂TMMPP, the starting material [Co^{II}(TTMPP)], and the cobalt complexes [Co^{III}(TTMPP)(DMAP)₂] have first been characterized by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, where the spectra display characteristic signals of the porphyrinic framework as well as the axial ligands DMAP.

In the IR spectra, the functional groups of the synthesized porphyrinic compounds were identified through the presence of characteristic vibrational bands.

Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) in positive mode further confirms the proposed structures of the cobalt porphyrin complexes

3.2 Structural study by X-ray diffraction

Figure 1. ORTEP view of the complex cation [Co^{III}(TTMPP)(DMAP)₂]⁺. Only the major occupancy positions are shown. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 30% probability level

4. CONCLUSION

Spectroscopic and single-crystal X-ray diffraction methods were used to successfully synthesize and analyze the cobalt porphyrin complex [Co(TTMP)(DMAP)]. The findings verified that axial coordination of DMAP led to the production of a hexacoordinated Co(III) species. Overall, this work shows how axial ligation significantly affects the supramolecular and structural characteristics of cobalt porphyrin complexes.

Acknowledge

We thank Dr. Xx for his/her support. This work was supported by the Office of Scientific Research Projects Coordination at University of Monastir, Tunisia

Author Contributions (Compulsory)

The author read and approved the final version of the paper. / All the authors equally contributed to this work. This paper is derived from the first author's doctoral dissertation thesis supervised by the second author. They all read and approved the final version of the paper.

Conflict of Interest (Compulsory)

The author declares no conflict of interest. / All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Review and Approval (Compulsory)

No ethical approval is required. / The research was reviewed and approved by the Board of Ethics of Monastir University

References

- [1] Giuseppe Genchi et al., "Prevalence of Cobalt in the Environment and Its Role in Biological Processes," *Biology*, 2023, 12(10), 1335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12101335>
- [2] Yin et al., "Recent Advances in Porphyrin-Based COFs Boosting CO₂ Photocatalytic and Electrocatalytic Conversion," *Nanomaterials*, 2025, 15, 1787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano15231787>
- [3] Mpakanyane et al., "The Design of Cobalt(II)-Porphyrin Nanohybrids for Electrochemical Sensing," *Electrocatalysis*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12678-025-00944-8>
- [4] Zhou et al., "Axial ligands tailoring the ORR activity of cobalt porphyrin," *Science Bulletin*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2019.07.003>
- [5] J.-F. Longevial et al., "Porphyrin derivatives in catalysis, molecular electronics and biomedicine," *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2018, 24, 15442–15460. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201801211>
- [6] J.-F. Longevial, S. Clément, J.A. Wytko, R. Ruppert, J. Weiss, S. Richeter, "Peripherally Metalated Porphyrins with Applications in Catalysis, Molecular Electronics and Biomedicine," *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2018, 24, 15442–15460. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201801211>
- [7] Y. Zhou, Y.-F. Xing, J. Wen, H.-B. Ma, F.-B. Wang, X.-H. Xia, "Axial ligands tailoring the ORR activity of cobalt porphyrin," *Science Bulletin*, 2019, 64, 1158–1166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2019.07.003>

- [8] SMART, SAINT, and SADABS, Bruker AXS Inc., Madison, WI, 2008 (n.d.)
- [9] A. Altomare, G. Cascarano, C. Giacovazzo, A. Guagliardi, M.C. Burla, G. Polidori, M. Camalli, SIRPOW.92 –a program for automatic solution of crystal structures by direct methods optimized for powder data, *Journal of Applied Crystallography* 27 (1994) 435–436, doi: 10.1107/S0021889894000221
- [10] G.M. Sheldrick, Crystal structure refinement with SHELXL, *Acta Cryst C* 71 (2015) 3–8, doi: 10.1107/S2053229614024218 .